

“Zimcorp” – A Collaborative Web Application for Enhancing Intracorporate Communication

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to discuss the significance of effective communication in organizations. Corporate web is extremely useful for communication and collaboration between the employees for successful functioning of any business organization. Using this tool helps in conveying and distributing necessary information among the employees of an organization and to post their ideas of how the project can be done, posting their queries, motivating each employee, compatibility between each team leaders and employees. It will help to minimize organizational conflict, cosy environment and enhance time management. This stands as a milestone for organisation as a whole network of efficient workplace.

Keywords: Strategies, Organizational, Facilitating, Objectives

I. INTRODUCTION

Communication is a means of effective organization. It strengthens the way of working in an intra-corporate environment. It is the blood flow of every organization. There is a necessary need in every work place to interact with each other for exclusive performance strategies based on organizational development. By creating this communication chain structure it automatically enhances coordination and elevate effective growth. As once the work surrounding was composed of physical space within employees and managers that lead to regular meetings and discussions this resulted in time consumption. But now in current scenario there is no longer space for

individual work environment. Organisations now explore workplace strategies to enhance collaborative space for employees and organisation to connect firmly. This tool consists of features such as discussion forums, chat boxes, analytical approach, dashboards, blogs, project discussion, employee's profile. This provides an intra-corporate efficient environment for the workers. This results in easy task allocation to the workers, communication and sound relationship between the employees and top level management.

II. Organisational Communication

Organisational communication is defined as transmitting related information and data about the task from the association to employees for interactive communication. Organizational communication is mainly based on the construction of a community within the work place to associate the task management and achievement status. Projects play a major role in the task activities on both the current and completed project discussion phase, where these strategies can be discussed on daily basis on chats and forums. Therefore this is the key mechanism for achieving coordination and development of the specified activities at distinct levels in the organisation. Organizational communication aims at linking related tasks, work units and divisions in the workplace. Also increases with task specialization and diversity in organizational structure.

III. Features

Job insecurity can be reduced and a way of efficient community space should be created so that employees feel their responsibility to the workplace. These features help in the way to execute their ideas of how the project can be delivered, posting queries, motivating their performance, compatibility among team leaders and members.

Figure 3.1 Task management chart

A. Forum

This discussion forum can bring together management and employees and allow for an open discussion on any topics and clarifications. Forums are also effective in archiving organisational communication to be used by the workers. It also facilitate in knowledge sharing. This will enable in posting queries related to workplace.

B. Intranet

An intranet is a private network that can be accessed by any authorised users within an organisation. It is mainly used for internal communication and collaboration. This result in a more flexible workforce and ensure all employees are working towards their comfort zone.

C. Dashboard

Dashboard is a visual display of the most important information needed to define one or more objectives. It consists of company details. A detailed comparison of the income each year as data automatically updated

Figure 3.2 Task Management/Activity

D. Blog

Blog is a place where employees can share their ideas, opinions, thoughts fast and in an informal way. It helps in broadcasting and highlighting an employee’s knowledge about a certain topic in organisation. It can also be frequently updated for general public interaction among the organisation.

E. Chat box

Chat box is a powerful tool where we can create a large platform for effective and friendly communication between every employee. It is the perfect tool for hosting online communication and coordinating teamwork. It is the most reliable messaging system.

F. Project Discussion

Project discussion allows user to quickly poll their friends on different project environment. Here this tool provide the details about the existing and also the current projects on going in the organisation, workers can also refer the details of the projects done.

IV. Pseudo code

Login as an admin or employee of the private organization

if *Admin*

- Calculate the performance of every employees
 - Calculate their project works
 - Get the input of every employees working hours
- else if *Employee*

- Login with employee id
- Check the ToDoList for upcoming work
- Add new ideas in the blog page
- Chat with the officials about some clarification
- Check out new events for today
- Determine the project discussion

else *New Employee*

- Login with the new registration
- Give the required details
- Get details of the completed projects
- Create new blogs and events
- Get the work for ongoing project

Update the status on the task completion phase
 The works hours will be automatically calculated
 Meeting notification will be displayed if conducted

Figure 3.3 Task Status

V. Comparison

ezTalks Meeting (Existing System)	Soft-Tech (Proposed System)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It provide online meeting facility ➤ A record and play back feature is provided for the purpose of future reference. ➤ Screen sharing page for better expressive of views ➤ Control and management feature about the meeting schedules 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Here we provide online chat box feature to communicate via chats other than conducting a meeting ➤ Here a project discussion phase provide a detailed view of the current and completed project detail for future reference ➤ We provide a forum and blog pages to easily share their thought in a friendly way and to broadcast their ideas ➤ Automatic Emergency alert feature for meeting to be conducted on time

Table 1

VI. Conclusion

Effective communication should be highly recommended to every organization in all the sectors of the economy. Private that is desirous of ensuring the success and efficiency of its workforce, should be conscious of implementing effective environment to their employees for better performances. Therefore, effective communication process should be an integral part of every organisation.

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